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Plant-soil synchrony in nutrient cycles: learning from natural ecosystems to design sustainable agrosystems

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1 *Preprint*

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3 *Plant-soil synchrony in nutrient cycles: learning from*
4 *natural ecosystems to design sustainable agrosystems*

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Glossary

Stoichiometric constraints refer to the fact that living organisms need several chemical elements (C, N, P etc.) in specific ratios for their biosynthesis (e.g., proteins).

Plant demand is the amount of nutrients needed to synthesize plant biomass from the carbon obtained by photosynthesis.

Soil supply is the amount of soluble nutrients released (from both inorganic and organic reserves) into the soil mainly by soil biota and assimilable by plant roots. Part of these soluble nutrients is also subject to losses by denitrification, volatilization and leaching.

Plant-soil synchrony describes the level of correspondence between plant demand and soil supply.

Systems of synchrony refer to the arrangements (organizations) of plants and soil biota, as well as the numerous biogeochemical functions they catalyze, contributing to increase the level of correspondence between plant demand and soil supply (high plant-soil synchrony).

Soil biota refers to all organisms living in soil except primary producers. It includes soil microbes and soil fauna.

Free-living soil decomposers correspond to soil microbes that are not attached to living plant roots and degrade soil organic matter for their energy and nutrient requirements. They can live within and outside the plant rhizosphere.

Microbial root symbionts correspond to microbes that are physically attached to plant roots for a close and long-term interaction. They include nitrogen-fixing bacteria present in the nodules of leguminous plants, and mycorrhizal fungi that are associated to roots of 80 % of all known terrestrial plant species.

Rhizodeposition is the organic matter deposited by roots in the rhizosphere including exudates (sugars, organic and amino acids, signal molecules etc), mucilage and dead root cells.

MAOM is the acronym of Mineral Associated Organic Matter. It corresponds to organic matter bound to soil minerals (clay, metal oxides and hydroxides) through different physicochemical interactions (electrostatic, covalent, hydrogen bridge etc).

M-microbes correspond to the functional type of microbes contributing to MAOM destruction and nutrient release (nutrient mineralization).

I- microbes correspond to the functional types of microbes contributing to MAOM formation and mineral nutrient immobilization.

FreeOM is the acronym of Free Organic Matter. It refers to the organic matter that is not bound to soil minerals and that accumulates either in the organic layer overlying the mineral soil or as particulate organic matter in the mineral soil.

Soil organic matter refers to all dead organic matter present in soil (fresh litter, rhizodepositions, MAOM and FreeOM).

83 **Abstract**

84 Redesigning agrosystems with more ecological regulations can help feed a growing population,
85 preserve soils for future productivity and reduce environmental impacts. However, guidelines
86 for redesigning agrosystems from natural systems are limited. Reviewing the last knowledge of
87 ecosystem functioning, we outlined four ecological systems synchronizing the supply of soluble
88 nutrients by soil biota to fluctuating plant nutrient demand. This synchrony limits deficiencies
89 and excesses of soluble nutrient, which usually penalize both production and regulating services
90 of agrosystems such as nutrient retention and soil carbon storage. We detail how ecological
91 systems promoting synchrony can be installed in agrosystems to improve their sustainability
92 and reduce the use of mineral fertilizers.

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97 One of the grand challenges of humankind is to feed a growing world population while
98 preserving soil assets for future productivity, reducing environmental impacts such as
99 greenhouse gas emissions, eutrophication and biodiversity loss, all under more extreme climate
100 conditions¹. Researchers and actors of the agricultural sector have driven many innovations to
101 increase the efficiency of agricultural management practices (e.g., precision fertilization)² or
102 transforming the cropping systems themselves (reduced tillage, rotation with permanent plant
103 cover, crop diversification) in an attempt to mitigate the ongoing degradation of soil health,
104 biodiversity and the environment³. In the latter context, natural or semi-natural ecosystems such
105 as grasslands and forests are increasingly being considered as benchmarks for redesigning
106 cropping systems⁴⁻⁶. Indeed, these ecosystems can produce large amount of biomass,
107 sometimes equivalent to that of high-input annual crops^{4,7-9}, while maintaining natural assets
108 such as soil organic matter^{4,10,11}, high levels of biodiversity¹² and key regulating services such
109 as water purification^{4,13} and carbon (C) storage¹⁴. However, effective guidelines for redesigning
110 cropping systems based on natural systems remain limited^{15,16}.

111 The higher sustainability of natural ecosystems has previously been linked to
112 characteristics such as higher plant diversity, higher root biomass, higher fungal:bacteria ratio,
113 and the increased efficiency of particular functions, e.g. improved soil exploration and resource
114 uptake by roots^{10,17}. However, ecosystems also show marked differences in their characteristics
115 such as dominant plant traits¹⁸ and soil microbial diversity¹⁹, which means that the type or level
116 of characteristics required for sustainable agricultural production cannot be easily generalized
117 and likely vary with pedoclimatic context. Moreover, ecosystem functioning results from
118 numerous interacting organisms and functions involved in C and nutrient cycling (Figure 1).
119 Therefore, the higher sustainability of natural ecosystems could reflect a greater coordination
120 between species and between biogeochemical functions (i.e., a better ecosystem organization),
121 rather than improvements in single functions or ecosystem characteristics.

122 Here we advocate that the design of cropping systems should consider the fact that the
123 productivity and sustainability of ecosystems are inextricably linked to the level of synchrony
124 between the supply of soluble nutrients by soil biota and plant demand for those soluble
125 nutrients. A low level of synchrony generates both periods of excess soluble nutrients with a
126 risk of nutrient loss, soil impoverishment and environmental pollution, and periods of nutrient
127 deficiency limiting plant development^{20,21}. In contrast, high synchrony promotes the conversion
128 of light energy to biomass by alleviating the nutrient limitation of plant growth, the closure of
129 nutrient cycles and the conservation, or even accumulation, of soil organic nutrient^{20,21}.
130 Asynchrony between soil supply and plant demand is common in cropping systems, leading to
131 increased nutrient losses and increased reliance on mineral fertilizers to maintain productivity²⁰⁻
132²². Since plant demand and soil supply depend on a high diversity of organisms and functions
133 characterized by different responses to environmental factors (Figure 1), it is not surprising that
134 the temporal variation in nutrient release from soil biota rarely coincides with the time course
135 of crop demand²¹. This raises the intriguing question of how multiple plant and soil functions
136 can be coordinated to achieve a high level of synchrony in natural ecosystems, and to what
137 extent this knowledge can be used to design sustainable agrosystems.

138 We propose here an integrated framework describing how designing sustainable
139 agrosystems by copying the synchronized biochemical functioning of natural ecosystems. This
140 framework is structured in two parts. By synthesizing the latest advances in ecology, we first
141 explain how multiple plant and soil functions can be coordinated towards a synchrony between
142 soil nutrient supply and plant demand in natural ecosystems. More specifically, we outline four
143 systems of synchrony and discuss their relative importance in regulating nutrient cycles
144 depending on the pedoclimatic context and the functional diversity of plants and soil microbes.
145 The second part of the framework details how a high level of synchrony can be promoted in
146 agrosystems. By using the knowledge from natural ecosystems, we identify the types of

147 synchrony systems to be promoted according to the pedoclimatic context, and suggest
 148 combinations of practices that could install them in cropping systems. A review of the last
 149 advances in agronomy shows that some of the practices suggested as promoting synchrony have
 150 already been tested and shown to be effective in reducing nutrient losses and fertilizer use and/or
 151 improving biomass production and soil C storage. However, our framework also highlighted
 152 several new management strategies based on plant and microbial functional traits that should
 153 help improve agrosystem sustainability, including in difficult pedoclimatic conditions (e.g.
 154 coarse-textured soils).

155
 156 **Figure 1.** The high level of synchrony between plant demand and soil supply characterizing natural ecosystems
 157 requires the coordination of numerous soil and plant functions. Plant demand corresponds to the amount of
 158 nutrients needed to convert the photosynthesis-derived carbon in biomass. It varies both over time and across
 159 species depending on multiple functions such as photosynthesis, organ formation and phenology, and factors such
 160 as the stoichiometric constraints of species and light intensity. Soil supply refers to the amount of soluble nutrients
 161 (mineral and organic), mainly released by soil biota comprising microbes and fauna. It varies over time and soil
 162 space depending on the prevalence of the various functions catalyzed by soil biota. Some functions increase soil
 163 nutrient supply (decomposition of soil organic matter -SOM-, biological N₂ fixation and nutrient release from
 164 minerals), while others decrease it (nutrient immobilization in microbial biomass and soil organic matter). A
 165 fraction of soluble nutrients can also be adsorbed as ions on the electrically charged surfaces of soil minerals but
 166 it remains available for plant uptake. The factors controlling soil supply are mostly different from those controlling
 167 plant demand, raising the issue of the plant demand-soil supply synchrony.

168 Two synchrony systems based on soil organic nutrient reserves

169 A significant part of plant nutrient uptake (over 80% for nitrogen, N) is obtained through
 170 organic matter recycling²³. The traditional view of nutrient cycling was that the mineralization
 171 of soil organic matter to mineral nutrients is the major bottleneck restricting nutrient supply to
 172 plants (Supplementary Box 1). Over the last twenty years, however, progress in isotopic and
 173 molecular tracing of C and N fluxes has highlighted the capacity of plants to overcome this
 174 bottleneck²⁴⁻²⁷. Plants have been shown to exert an influence on all soil nutrient fluxes through
 175 a combination of processes altering the accessibility of soil resources and the activity of soil
 176 microbial communities²⁸. These processes comprise rhizodeposition, nutrient uptake, litter
 177 chemistry and mycorrhizal associations^{24,25,29}
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179 Nevertheless, an apparent paradox remains regarding the synchrony between soil supply
180 and plant demand. On the one hand, root activities such as rhizodeposition stimulate the
181 microbial decomposition of soil organic matter and the release of soluble nutrients through the
182 so-called rhizosphere priming effect^{24,27,43}. These root activities are primarily fueled by
183 photosynthesis-derived C. Therefore, an increase in plant photosynthesis and nutrient demand
184 (Figure 1) induces an increase in root activities and nutrient release from soil organic matter,
185 suggesting a supply-demand synchrony. On the other hand, root activities are known to also
186 accelerate microbial immobilization of mineral nutrients, and nutrient sequestration in soil
187 organic matter^{24,49}. This contributes to reduce soil nutrient availability when plant demand
188 increases, suggesting a supply-demand asynchrony. This paradox can be resolved by
189 considering two systems of synchrony where the antagonistic nutrient fluxes driving soil
190 nutrient availability for plants (decomposition/nutrient release *versus* nutrient
191 immobilization/sequestration) are coordinated to coincide with the time course of plant
192 demand. These two systems are based on the two types of soil organic matter built by plant-soil
193 systems, namely the mineral-associated organic matter -MAOM- *versus* litter-based free
194 organic matter -FreeOM-, which are associated to two different nutrient cycles^{29,42}.

195 **Synchrony based on mineral-associated organic matter (Sync-MAOM)**

196 This synchrony system is promoted by resource-acquisitive⁵⁰ plant species characterized by
197 rapid growth, high tissue turnover and rhizodeposition²⁴, and litter with chemistry conducive to
198 decomposition, e.g. low content of lignin and condensed tannins, low C:N³⁷. Organic matter
199 deposited by plants is rapidly decomposed by free-living soil decomposers that release smaller
200 organic compounds characterized by lower-energy and higher-nutrient contents^{51,52}. These
201 compounds self-assemble, adsorb on soil minerals and also precipitate with metal cations (Fe,
202 Al, Si), which further increases the cost to access them (secretion of exoenzymes and/or
203 ligands)^{53,54}. Accumulating in soils over thousands of years^{55,56}, these compounds constitute a
204 large reservoir of MAOM⁵⁷.

205 Resource-acquisitive plants mainly absorb nutrients in mineral forms whose availability
206 depends on the mineralization and immobilization activities^{29,47} of two broad functional types
207 of microbes^{28,58}(Figure 2). It has recently been reported that these microbial types use, and
208 compete for, plant rhizodeposits and litter as source of energy, but have different nutrient
209 acquisition strategies^{28,59}. The C to nutrient ratio of plant material is often too high for microbial
210 nutrient needs, implying that microbes have to find a complementary source of nutrients³². We
211 refer to mineralizer microbes (M-microbes) as those able to acquire nutrients by decomposing
212 MAOM through the secretion of exoenzymes and ligands, e.g. some members from the
213 *Tremellomycetes* class^{28,60}. Their activities lead to net destruction of MAOM and release of
214 mineral nutrients after excretion of excess nutrients and microbial turnover^{28,58}. The
215 immobilizers (I-microbes) are not able to decompose MAOM and assimilate the nutrients they
216 need from the soil solution, e.g. some members from the *Massilia* genus^{28,61}. Their activities
217 lead to MAOM formation and mineral nutrient immobilization^{58,59}.

218 These two microbial types characterized here according to their role on soil nutrient
219 fluxes are consistent with ecological strategies, microbial traits, and microbial limitations
220 previously described by microbiologists^{28,62}. M-microbes refer to slow-growing microbes
221 characterized by high investment in resource acquisition and low carbon use efficiency⁵⁹. Their
222 low carbon use efficiency, combined with the fact they have potentially unlimited access to
223 MAOM nutrients, means that M-microbes are primarily limited by the availability of energy
224 (rhizodeposits, litter)^{28,58}. In contrast, I-microbes refer to fast-growing microbes characterized
225 by low investment in resource acquisition, high carbon use efficiency and limitation by nutrient
226 availability^{28,58}.

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230 **Figure 2.** Synchrony between plant nutrient demand and soil supply of mineral nutrients through mineralization
 231 of mineral-associated organic matter (Sync-MAOM). This example describes the seasonal change in plant demand
 232 and soil supply. The numbers illustrate the chronology of events in response to an increased (left panel) or
 233 decreased (right panel) plant demand. The letters M and I indicate the two functional types of microbes controlling
 234 the availability of mineral nutrients in soils (microbial mineralizers and immobilizers, respectively). Green, blue
 235 and brown arrows describe flows of plant material, mineral nutrients and MAOM, respectively. For clarity, the
 236 mechanisms of MAOM decomposition such as the secretion of extracellular enzymes and ligands by microbes or
 237 roots are not represented. The synchrony presented here contributes to maintaining very low concentrations of
 238 soluble nutrients and hence low nutrient losses by leaching or denitrification (losses not represented).

239 We suggest that the activities of M- and I-microbes constitute a supply chain of mineral
 240 nutrients contributing to satisfy the plant nutrient demand and conserve nutrients in ecosystem
 241 (Figure 2). The heterogeneous distribution of roots, organic matter of contrasted quality and
 242 communities of M- and I-microbes in soil create hotspots of nutrient immobilization and
 243 mineralization^{41,63}. Between these soil microsites, several hundred kilograms of mineral N per
 244 hectare are typically diffusing each year⁴⁹. These quantities exceed the yearly N requirements
 245 of most plant species. Plants efficiently compete for mineral nutrient uptake with I-microbes
 246 thanks to their higher lifespan and their root system that explores heterogeneous soil conditions
 247 with the help of mycorrhizal fungi⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. Moreover, the two nutrient fluxes of the supply chain
 248 (mineralization & immobilization) may adjust to plant demand. Photosynthesis determines
 249 plant demand but also plant material inputs and nutrient uptake^{29,44}. As a result, soil resource
 250 availability is continuously modified according to the plant demand with important
 251 consequences for M- and I-microbes activity (Figure 2). As plant demand increases, the greater
 252 uptake of mineral nutrients by plants reduces nutrient immobilization by I-microbes as well as
 253 their use of plant material (Figure 2, left panel). At the same time rhizodeposition of energy-
 254 rich substrates is increased and the ligands present in rhizodeposits desorb organic matter from
 255 minerals making them more accessible to M-microbes⁶⁷. More energy is available to M-
 256 microbes stimulating their decomposition activities and release of mineral nutrients from
 257 MAOM, an effect named rhizosphere priming^{44,58,68}. Conversely, when plant demand decreases
 258 (Figure 2 right panel), the mineral nutrients “left over” by plants induce a rapid development of
 259 I-microbes. More I-microbes decrease the energy availability for M-microbes thus increasing
 260 nutrient immobilization over mineralization.

261 Numerous studies support the existence of this synchrony system. A common garden
262 experiment comparing 12 grassland plant species with contrasted photosynthetic activities
263 reported that gross N mineralization (soil supply) adjusted to the demand of each of these
264 species⁴⁴. Recent syntheses showed that enhanced plant photosynthesis and plant demand for
265 nutrients under elevated CO₂ induce both an increase in gross N mineralization²⁷ and a decrease
266 in soil organic matter stock⁶⁹. Moreover, a decrease in plant photosynthesis in response to plant
267 shading/cutting induces a reduction in soil organic matter mineralization (soil supply) within
268 24 hours^{70,71}, supporting the idea of a high-speed synchrony. In many ecosystems, the
269 mineralization to immobilization ratio changes during the season in line with changes in plant
270 demand; immobilization dominates during the winter (low demand) whereas mineralization
271 dominates during spring-summer (high demand)^{72,73}. These functional changes have been
272 shown to be correlated to changes in microbial community structure^{72,73} supporting the idea of
273 a synchrony driven by plant-microbes interactions.

274 **Synchrony based on free organic matter (Sync-FreeOM)**

275 This synchrony system is promoted by resource-conservative plant species⁵⁰ characterized by
276 slow growth⁷⁴, low tissue turnover and rhizodeposition^{44,74}, and litter with high C:N ratio and
277 high content of lignin and condensed tannins³⁷. This litter chemistry decreases the return on
278 investment of decomposers (energy yield by decomposers once the investment in exoenzymes
279 have been considered)⁵⁹ slowing down their activities and litter decomposition. Moreover,
280 condensed tannins present in litter are able to complex small nutrient-rich organic compounds
281 such as plant protein, exoenzymes and residues of microbial necromass⁷⁵ protecting them
282 against decomposition and leaching. The accumulation of slowly-decomposing litter
283 complexing small molecules contributes to the build-up of large reserves of organic nutrients,
284 especially in heathland and cold ecosystems^{76,77}. These organic matter forms are mainly free of
285 soil minerals (FreeOM), accumulating in the organic layer and as particulate organic matter⁷⁸
286 in the mineral soil (Figure 3) for decades-centuries^{76,79}.

287 The activity of free-living decomposers releases little mineral N because the C/N ratios
288 of litter and FreeOM are high relative to decomposer biomass⁴¹. To compensate for this lack of
289 mineral nutrient, the roots of conservative plant species and their associated mycorrhizal fungi
290 have developed the capacity to absorb soluble organic nutrients such as amino acids^{41,42}
291 released by the activity of microbial exoenzymes, pre-empting their uptake by decomposers.
292 Moreover, we suggest that conservative woody species may actively control the
293 depolymerization of FreeOM in soluble organic nutrients to satisfy their nutrient demand during
294 the growing season (left panel Figure 3). Indeed, recent studies have shown that these plants
295 associate with ericoid or ectomycorrhizal fungi which have large enzymatic abilities⁸⁰ allowing
296 them to depolymerize the FreeOM^{25,81,82}. Mycorrhizal fungi also have the capacity to inhibit or
297 stimulate the activity of free-living soil decomposers and thus their release of soluble organic
298 nutrients⁸³. By trading photosynthate-C against nutrients with their mycorrhizal partners,
299 conservative woody species may modulate the rate of FreeOM depolymerization and nutrient
300 supply to their needs.

301 Conservative herbaceous plants can also lead to the accumulation of FreeOM and take up
302 soluble organic nutrients in the tropics as well as in temperate or cold environments^{79,84,85}.
303 Endo-mycorrhizal fungi associated to herbaceous plants can help to satisfy plant nutrient
304 demand by absorbing soluble organic nutrients released by the activity of free decomposers.
305 However, contrary to ericoid and ectomycorrhizal fungi, endo-mycorrhizae have no or little
306 degradative capability⁸⁶. Therefore, it remains unclear whether these plants can control the
307 release of nutrient from FreeOM and how they would make it. An increased mowing of
308 conservative species has been shown to accelerate FreeOM decomposition and N cycling^{87,88},
309 suggesting that roots of conservative plants have some control over soil nutrient fluxes.

310 Conservative herbaceous plants have been suggested to modulate nutrient fluxes by shaping the
 311 activity of free-living decomposers through their associations with endo-mycorrhizal fungi and
 312 endophytes^{86,89}.

313
 314 **Figure 3.** Synchrony between plant nutrient demand and soil supply of dissolved organic nutrient through
 315 depolymerization of free organic matter (Sync-FreeOM). This example illustrates the case of conservative woody
 316 plants associated with ectomycorrhizal or ericoid fungi. We describe the response of these ecosystems to seasonal
 317 changes including a long period of plant inactivity (e.g., alpine ecosystems). Mycorrhizal fungi mine nutrients in
 318 FreeOM in function to the plant demand. The activity of free-living decomposers contributes to the building of
 319 FreeOM during period of plant inactivity, and to supply of soluble organic nutrients during period of plant growth.
 320 The numbers show the chronology of events in response to a high plant demand (left panel). Green, blue and
 321 brown arrows describe flows of plant material, soluble organic nutrients and FreeOM, respectively. The
 322 synchrony presented here contributes to maintaining very low concentrations of soluble nutrients and hence low
 323 nutrient losses by leaching or denitrification (losses not represented).

324 **Synchrony based on inorganic nutrients retrieved from the atmosphere and**
 325 **minerals (Sync-Inorganic)**

326 Aside from soil organic reserves, plants can access several other sources of nutrients for which
 327 supply-demand regulations can occur. A classic example is N uptake from the atmosphere by
 328 legumes which depends on the rapid transfer of photosynthates to root nodules where Rhizobia
 329 carry out the costly process of N₂ fixation⁹⁰. Given the dependency of nodules to plant C,
 330 conditions enhancing photosynthesis (plant demand) such as the increase in light intensity or
 331 atmospheric CO₂ usually lead to an increase in N₂ fixation⁹¹. Conversely, factors reducing
 332 photosynthesis reduce N₂ fixation⁹¹. Photosynthesis modulates not only nodule number and
 333 growth, but also the activity of nitrogenase⁹⁰, leading to a fast (hours) synchrony between plant
 334 demand and microbial N₂ fixation.

335 Rock, soil minerals and precipitates represent a crucial source of phosphorus (P),
 336 potassium, calcium, magnesium, and iron for plants⁹². These nutrients are not directly available
 337 to plants, and first need to be solubilized (P precipitates) or released from the mineral matrix
 338 (rock) through physical and chemical weathering before being absorbed by plants. Roots can
 339 directly accelerate this nutrient mobilization through the secretion of protons and ligands
 340 solubilizing and desorbing nutrients from the mineral phase. A synthesis of recent research

341 showed that rhizodeposition also supports large communities of root-associated microbes that
342 accelerate weathering of minerals, amplifying the nutrient availability to plants by several
343 orders of magnitude⁴⁵. For example, mycorrhizal hyphae exert a mechanical pressure that
344 provokes physical distortion of the mineral lattice structure facilitating subsequent chemical
345 alteration⁴⁵. Diverse microbes promote the dissolution of the mineral matrix^{45,92}. All these
346 mechanisms of nutrient supply depend on the delivery of energy by plants that trade energy
347 against nutrients with microbes, in particular mycorrhizal fungi⁹³. Overall, plant photosynthesis
348 determines the amount of energy that can be allocated to microbes carrying out mineral
349 dissolution/weathering, enabling a synchrony between plant demand and nutrient supply from
350 minerals.

351 Synchrony on multiple nutrients simultaneously promoted by a common market 352 (Sync-Market)

353 In the previous sections, we summarized how the nutrient supply by soil microbes (all nutrients
354 confounded) may adjust to overall plant nutrient demand controlled by the amount of
355 photosynthetic C available for biosynthesis. However, plants as well as microbes need a variety
356 of nutrients in specific ratios⁹⁴. These stoichiometric constraints raise the question of a
357 synchrony acting simultaneously on multiple nutrients. The different synchrony systems
358 outlined above appear unable, individually, to bring nutrients in the ratios suitable for plant
359 needs. Although research on the coupling of multiple elements in ecosystems is still in its
360 infancy, a number of empirical results support the existence of multiple nutrient synchrony^{95,96}.
361 Plants can balance the macro- and micro-nutrients they receive by modulating the energy they
362 allocate to microbial partners controlling acquisition pathways for particular nutrients⁹⁶. For
363 example, a lack of P triggers a greater allocation of C to mycorrhizal fungi and associated
364 microbes which secrete phosphatases or protons to acquire soil P⁹⁶.

365 Multiple synchrony could also occur through a common market of nutrients (Sync-
366 Market, Figure 4). Mycorrhizal fungi form common networks that act as highways for the
367 movement of C and nutrients, redistributing them across space and between plants of either the
368 same or different species^{97,98}. This redistribution suggests that mutualistic microbes not only
369 trade their nutrients with the plant they are directly associated with, but also with other
370 symbionts that are themselves connected to other plants that might have complementary
371 nutrient needs (e.g., different ratios between the elements constituting plant biomass) and/or
372 local soil supply consecutive to different plant nutrient acquisition strategies (e.g., root depth,
373 quantity/quality of exudates, litter chemistry). This multi-partner trading creates a common
374 carbon and nutrient market with beneficial effects for the nutrition and growth of interconnected
375 plants and microbes⁹⁷. Indeed, the capacity of mycorrhizal fungi to trade the various soil-
376 acquired nutrients against plant-acquired energy is enhanced by this market. The nutrient
377 redistribution between plants by the mycorrhizal network is better able to satisfy the plant
378 demand in multiple nutrients and limit local excess of soluble nutrients. Therefore, the common
379 market can maximize synchrony at different scales (from plant to ecosystem) and for several
380 elements simultaneously, explaining the positive effects of common mycorrhizal networks
381 observed on plant nutrition and growth⁹⁷.

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389 **Figure 4.** Synchrony between plant demand and soil supply on multiple nutrients can be facilitated by a common
 390 nutrient market supported by mycorrhizal networks. The symbols (triangle, circle, star) illustrate different
 391 nutrients. The local soil supply represents the amount of soluble nutrients delivered by the soil biota (from organic
 392 and inorganic nutrient reserves) before the nutrient redistribution between plants through the common market.
 393 This local soil supply can vary with local soil characteristics, root depth and plant nutrient acquisition strategies.
 394 The nutrient redistribution between plants by the mycorrhizal network is better able to satisfy the plant demand in
 395 multiple nutrients and limit local excess of soluble nutrients.

396 Influence of abiotic and biotic factors on synchrony

397 Pedoclimatic context and plant functional types

398 Building on the recent scientific advances, we propose a framework with four systems capable
 399 of synchronizing the soil nutrient supply to plant demand at a range of time scales (from hours
 400 to seasons). Two systems (Sync-FreeOM, Sync-Inorganic) are based on plant-products such as
 401 litter or nodule-supporting tissues of legumes, and microbial symbionts that tightly interact with
 402 plant roots such that they can be considered as the extended phenotype of certain plants⁹⁹. For
 403 the remaining systems (Sync-MAOM, Sync-Market), synchrony emerges from diffuse
 404 interactions between distinct functional types of microbes and plants and therefore can be
 405 considered as ecosystemic regulations. These four synchrony systems co-occur in most
 406 ecosystems, their relative importance in regulating nutrient cycles depending on pedoclimatic
 407 context, plant functional type and biodiversity level (Figure 5 & 6).

408 Sync-inorganic plays a key role in young soils where organic nutrient reserves are
 409 limited and soil inorganic nutrient reserves dominate (Figure 5). Sync-inorganic is also
 410 determined by the ability of the plant community to retrieve nutrients from atmosphere and soil
 411 minerals, which depends, for example, on the proportion of legumes. The contribution of
 412 synchrony systems based on soil organic reserves (Sync-MAOM, Sync-FreeOM) increases
 413 with soil age as organic matter accumulates and inorganic reserves are depleted.

414 Sync-MAOM is promoted by resource-acquisitive plant species producing litter with a
 415 chemistry conducive to rapid decomposition by microbes that release the organic compounds

416 leading to MAOM formation. This formation depends on interactions with minerals, and the
 417 contribution of Sync-MAOM increases as soil particle size decreases and mineral reactivity
 418 increases¹⁰⁰. Moreover, Sync-MAOM requires a regular plant supply of energy-rich substrates
 419 to M- and I-microbes. Thus, Sync-MAOM may dominate where climatic conditions are
 420 favorable to plant activity most of the year.

421 Sync-FreeOM is promoted by resource-conservative species producing litters with a
 422 chemistry unfavorable to decomposition. When rich in condensed tannins, this litter
 423 complexes the small organic compounds released by microbes building large reserves of
 424 FreeOM. This contributes to nutrient conservation even under context of low MAOM formation
 425 potential and periods of plant inactivity. Thus, Sync-FreeOM is expected to dominate in coarse-
 426 textured soils and/or under climates with long season(s) without plant activity^{76,77}.

427 **Figure 5.** Relative importance for ecosystem functioning of the synchrony systems based on nutrients retrieved
 428 from atmosphere and soil minerals (Sync-Inorganic) and from soil organic nutrient (Sync-Organic) in relation to
 429 pedoclimatic contexts and plant functional type. The Sync-Organic is composed of two distinct synchrony systems
 430 mobilizing different types of soil organic matter, namely the mineral-associated organic matter (Sync—MAOM)
 431 and the free organic matter (Sync-FreeOM). The change of the dominant organic nutrient reserve (MAOM versus
 432 FreeOM) can be paralleled to the change in humus forms (Mull, Moder and Mor) described by soil scientists
 433 along environmental gradients.
 434

435 Sync-Market is induced when different plants connected by common mycorrhizal
 436 networks have complementary nutrient needs and/or local soil nutrient supply (Supplementary
 437 material 2). Thus, the contribution of Sync market is expected to increase with spatial
 438 heterogeneity (from nanoscale to soil profile) of soil nutrient reserves (organic and inorganic)
 439 and their elemental composition (e.g., N/P/S ratio). Plant functional diversity (e.g. plant with
 440 different C/N ratio in biomass, root depth and root architecture, quantity/quality of exudates)

441 within the canopy promotes Sync-Market by increasing the complementary effects between
442 plants in terms of nutrient needs and local soil nutrient supply. The contribution of Sync-Market
443 to ecosystem functioning is also determined by the capacity of plants to form common
444 mycorrhizal networks.

445 **Biodiversity: a key asset promoting synchrony**

446 Higher plant and microbial diversity improve multiple ecosystem functions such as primary
447 production, nutrient retention and soil C storage¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰⁴ that are related to synchrony. Recent
448 evidence also indicates that the higher primary production promoted by plant diversity is
449 associated with an improved soil nutrient supply^{105,106}. We propose that biodiversity could
450 promote synchrony across scales ranging from individual plants to whole ecosystems, through
451 three non-exhaustive pathways.

452 *Biodiversity promotes synchrony through the functional complementarity of organisms.*
453 Synchrony systems clearly show an ecological division of labor¹⁰³ that may emerge from
454 evolutionary processes^{81,107}: each function of the system is carried out by specific groups of
455 biota such as organic nutrient reserve formation (I-microbes, conservative plants) and
456 decomposition (M-microbes, ectomycorrhizal & ericoid fungi), N₂ fixation (Rhizobium,
457 legumes) etc. The maintenance of these functional groups is fundamental for the synchrony
458 generated by each of these systems. Moreover, co-occurrence of plant species with different
459 nutrient strategies¹⁰⁸ (e.g., legumes/non-legumes, acquisitive/conservative, P-mobilizing-
460 plants) is also expected to induce different synchrony systems. The proximity of roots of
461 neighboring plants with different strategies facilitates nutrient transfer from plant to plant for
462 their mutual benefit in terms of nutrition and growth¹⁰⁹. This nutrient transfer takes place at
463 different time scales (hours to years) according to the processes involved¹⁰⁹, including nutrient
464 exchanges across mycorrhizal networks (Sync-Market), direct transfer of root exudates and
465 decomposition of plant materials. The exchange of N and P between legumes and P-mobilizing
466 plants is a classic example of plant-plant interactions which improve overall plant-soil
467 synchrony. More broadly, a high functional diversity of microbes and plants promotes both the
468 existence of - and the interaction between - synchrony systems with complementary roles in
469 ecosystems. Sync-Inorganic brings nutrients from atmosphere and bedrock to the ecosystem
470 while sync-MAOM and sync-FreeOM accumulate these nutrients in organic reserves, limiting
471 nutrient loss and allowing nutrient recycling when needed by plants. These synchrony systems
472 create major nutrient sources for plants while Sync-Market helps to balance the proportion of
473 different nutrients supplied in relation to the multiple element requirement of plants.

474 *Biodiversity facilitates synchrony by ensuring the temporal and spatial stability of plant-soil*
475 *interactions.* Synchrony requires that the connection between plants and microbes is maintained
476 in space and time. Given that species can occupy different niches, this space-to-time occupation
477 by plants and microbes often depends on species diversity. For example, soil occupation at
478 various soil depths but also across coarse and fine spatial scales requires multiple plant species
479 with contrasted root architecture and traits¹¹⁰. Succession of plant species with different
480 phenology contributes to maintaining a permanent plant cover in diversified ecosystems¹¹¹ and
481 a continuous energy supply to microbes, which is particularly important for sync-MAOM
482 (Figure 2). Importantly, increased diversity will also promote temporal and spatial stability by
483 promoting functional redundancy among species conferring greater resistance to environmental
484 fluctuation and disturbance overtime¹¹².

485 *Biodiversity stabilizes resource-exchange mutualisms.* We detailed several systems of
486 synchrony based on mutualism between plants and their microbial symbionts, and the
487 subsequent resource exchanges (e.g., Sync-Market). The maintenance of such mutualisms is
488 not obvious from an evolutionary point of view : any partner that invests less in the resource
489 exchange would have an immediate benefit, while the cost (lower partner abundance or activity)
490 would be shared by all, creating a classical tragedy of the commons¹¹³. We suggest that

491 diversity on both sides (plants and microbes) facilitates the maintenance of the resource
492 exchange. Indeed, the diversity of partners allows the possibility of partner choice and
493 reward/sanction, known to stabilize this type of mutualistic interaction^{113–115}.

494 **Plant plasticity and adaptations to unbalanced soil supply**

495 Despite existing mechanisms that facilitate supply-demand synchrony, strong spatial and
496 temporal variations in soil nutrient availability or plant demand generated by exogenous factors
497 such as animal excretion or extreme climatic events can induce transient periods of asynchrony
498 (excess or deficiency)^{116,117}. Insufficient soil supply in relation to the demand of a given plant
499 may also arise due to limiting nutrient reserves in soil and to localized plant-plant competition
500 for nutrients¹¹⁸. Plants can respond in two ways to unbalanced soil supply:

501 *Changes in physiology and morphology to enhance acquisition of limiting resources.* Plants are
502 able to adapt their physiology and morphology over short-time scales (hours-weeks) in response
503 to nutrient availability¹¹⁹. Under high nutrient supply, plant allocation of C and nutrients shifts
504 towards greater investment in shoots and photosynthetic proteins enhancing C acquisition¹²⁰.
505 In contrast, under low nutrient supply, plants promote nutrient acquisition and nutrient supply
506 from microbes by increasing root-to-shoot ratios, up-regulating root membrane transporters,
507 and changing root architecture and exudation^{121,122}.

508 *Nutrient storage.* When supply exceeds plant demand, many plant species adopt a luxury
509 nutrient uptake¹²³. These excess nutrients are stored in vacuoles in the short-term (days), or in
510 large storage organs such as rhizomes for remobilization several months-years later during
511 periods of insufficient soil supply¹²⁴. Reserves play a central role in the nutrition of perennial
512 plants, with remobilized N from previous year storage often representing more than 50% of N
513 recovered in new shoots¹²⁴. At the ecosystem scale, plant nutrient storage presents the same
514 advantages as synchrony since it promotes i) biomass production by alleviating the nutrient
515 limitation of plants and ii) nutrient retention by preventing accumulation of soluble nutrients in
516 soil. Plant reserves can also support the rapid recovery of photosynthesis and root activities
517 following disturbances¹²⁴ helping to maintain synchrony in these disturbed ecosystems.

518 **Implications for agrosystems**

519 **Fertility: an emerging property of plant-soil interactions**

520 Most definitions of soil fertility refer to the inherent capacity of a soil to sustain plant growth
521 and production by providing nutrients in adequate amounts and in suitable proportions¹²⁵. We
522 argue that recent work on plant-soil synchrony calls for an in-depth revision of this concept
523 because 1) plants can influence the quantity and proportion of soluble nutrients they receive
524 from soil *via* at least four systems of synchrony, and 2) soil nutrient supply should be considered
525 in relation to the fluctuating plant demand. Hence, nutrient supply from soil is not an inherent
526 property of soil but an emerging property of plant-soil interactions, even if soil characteristics
527 influence the nature and efficiency of these interactions (Figure 5). This has a practical
528 consequence: depending on the plant species and microbial taxa present and their ability to
529 influence soil nutrient supply, the same soil can support different levels of biomass production
530 as underlined in several experiments^{24,42}. It may also explain why soils defined as infertile can
531 support similar levels of biomass production as soils defined as fertile in some cases^{126,127}.
532 Identifying plant species capable of stimulating soil nutrient supply *via* synchrony systems
533 opens avenues towards ecological intensification of plant production.

534 **Managing synchrony to ensure both productivity and sustainability**

535 There is a great diversity of management approaches currently being explored to reinforce the
536 sustainability of agriculture (no or reduced tillage, organic farming, crop rotation, conservation
537 agriculture, permaculture...), yet finding efficient combinations of agroecosystem features for
538 a given pedoclimatic and socio-economic context remains difficult. The adoption of
539 “sustainable” practices does not always solve asynchrony issues. For instance, the incorporation

540 of legumes as green manure in rotation can lead to N losses as high as mineral fertilizers²⁰,
541 though this practice has the advantage of reducing the use of mineral N fertilizers whose
542 production generates greenhouse gases. Moreover, management practices often appear to
543 involve trade-offs or offsets between expected outcomes, for instance between yield and
544 greenhouse gas emissions, between soil C storage and emission of N₂O¹²⁸. Focusing on plant-
545 soil synchrony can help address these difficulties by guiding the changes to be made in
546 agrosystems to make them sustainably productive; understanding when and how synchrony is
547 enhanced is needed for management decisions. Analyzing the four synchrony systems, we have
548 identified the types of synchrony systems to be promoted according to the pedoclimatic context
549 (Figure 5 & supplementary material 2), and suggest combinations of practices that could install
550 them in cropping systems (Figure 6).

551 In young soils (e.g., Andosols), where inorganic reserves are high and organic reserves
552 can be low (Figure 5), management options should give greater importance to Sync-inorganic,
553 for example, by incorporating a high proportion of legumes and plant species mobilizing
554 nutrients from soil minerals through their rhizodeposition and association with mycorrhizae.
555 With organic nutrient accumulation and depletion of inorganic nutrient reserves as soils evolve,
556 agricultural practices should promote Sync-organic, for example by introducing species with
557 high rhizodeposition of energy-rich C for microbes (MAOM-sync; Figure 6). In the longer-
558 term, the inorganic and organic reserves of some rock-originated nutrients (e.g., P) can limit
559 synchrony in the topsoil of highly-weathered soils (e.g., Ferralsols). In these soils, synchrony
560 can be enhanced by including deep-rooting species capable of mobilizing the nutrients from
561 bedrock and redistribute them to the topsoil (Figure 6). Recent studies have shown the
562 possibility of stimulating different nutrient acquisition pathways (organic-P mineralization,
563 inorganic-P dissolution, N₂ fixation) through the selection of specific plant traits (N₂-fixation
564 efficiency, but also types of exudates)^{129,130}. It has also been reported that the level of soil
565 weathering determines the type of diversification and nutrient acquisition strategies able to
566 enhance ecosystem productivity and sustainability¹³⁰. In this study, legumes increased biomass
567 production (+18%) in Andosols but not in Ferralsols, while soil-P-mobilizing tree species
568 increased biomass production(+39%) and soil C stock(+26%) in Ferralsols but not in
569 Andosols¹³⁰.

570 Current industrial grain production systems are mostly based on fast-growing
571 acquisitive plant species¹³¹ generating MAOM-type soil organic matter. Given that the sync-
572 MAOM system requires a continuous C input from plants to microbes (Figure 2 & 5), practices
573 promoting a permanent plant cover in annual cropping systems could enhance synchrony.
574 Along a gradient of increasing novelty, these practices include lengthening of crop rotations,
575 cover/relay cropping and introduction of perennial grain crops (Figure 6). In agreement with
576 this idea, meta-analyses have shown that cover cropping reduces nitrate leaching by 70% on
577 average¹³² and increase soil organic C by 15.5%¹³³, provided the cover crop is not a pure legume
578 stand. Indeed, plant materials must have a carbon to nutrient ratio high enough to stimulate
579 nutrient immobilization by I-microbes (Figure 2).

580 In view of the involvement of soil minerals in MAOM formation, the synchrony system
581 that most crop species may generate (Sync-MAOM) is inadequate for coarse-textured soils with
582 low mineral reactivity. This explains why ecosystem conversion to cropping induces faster and
583 higher losses of C and N in sandy than in clay soils¹³⁴. Traditional management practices such
584 as extensive heathland grazing show that sandy soils can support sustainable production when
585 conservative plants are present (Sync-FreeOM, Figure 6)¹³⁵. We suggest that the sustainability
586 of many agrosystems or forestry systems established on coarse-textured soils may be improved
587 by introducing conservative species. These conservative species can be grown alone or in
588 association with acquisitive species such as annual crops (e.g., intercropping). In these
589 associations, the litter of conservative species will compensate the lack of reactive soil minerals

590 by chemically binding small organic nutrients released by microbes, preventing their leaching
591 (Figure 3). Rhizodeposition from acquisitive crop species will induce higher mineralization-
592 immobilization fluxes (Figure 2) allowing them to feed on mineral nutrients. The feasibility of
593 such intercropping is supported by the co-existence of resource-acquisitive and resource-
594 conservative species within many different ecosystems, including in coarse-textured soils¹³⁶.
595 However, research is needed to quantify the effect of such associations in an agricultural context
596 involving disturbances and species with particular traits¹³¹. The other strength of conservative
597 species is to maintain a high level of synchrony even when the ecosystem faces long period of
598 plant inactivity (*Sync-FreeOM versus Sync-MAOM*, Figure 5). Therefore, the use of
599 conservative species could be a way to promote agrosystem sustainability in situations where
600 maintaining an active plant cover throughout the year (condition for *Sync-MAOM*) is not
601 possible due to climatic, economic or technical constraints.

602 By coupling complementary synchrony systems, the association of plant species with
603 different nutrient economies (legumes/non-legumes; acquisitive/conservative; organic-P-
604 mobilizing-plants...) could increase the overall level of synchrony in agrosystems. Plant
605 associations can be implemented over time (crop rotation) and space (intercropping)(Figure 6).
606 The complementary effects between plant species can be facilitated by mycorrhizal networks
607 and the resulting common nutrient market (Figure 4), which depends on a combination of
608 practices (Figure 6). Although current plant associations are made with limited knowledge on
609 the nutrient economy of plants, recent meta-analyses confirm the strong positive impact of crop
610 associations on agrosystem productivity and sustainability¹³⁷⁻¹³⁹. For example, grain yields in
611 annual intercropping systems have been shown to be on average 22% higher than in
612 corresponding monocultures and have greater year-to-year stability^{137,140}. This over yielding
613 can be ascribed to a soil nutrient supply better synchronized with plant demand, with plant
614 uptake of P and N increased by 24% and 15-29% under intercropping relative to
615 monocultures^{138,141}. Studies have estimated that, for the same yields, current intercropping
616 systems can reduce the fertilizer requirement by 12% for P¹³⁸ and up to 44% for N¹³⁹. Another
617 example is the simultaneous insertion of grain legumes and cover crops in long rotations that
618 can reduce N requirements by 49-61% (according to species) with no detrimental effect on
619 wheat yield and grain quality¹⁴². Until now, most of the associations tested were limited to two
620 species, but some farmers mix more than ten species (Figure 6). These crops are harvested as
621 fodder or consumed on site by animals, promoting nutrient recycling and preservation of soil
622 organic nutrient reserves over time.

623 Significant amounts of nutrients leave croplands in harvested products and losses
624 through leaching and denitrification (e.g., export of on average 120 kg N and 30 kg P per hectare
625 for a wheat grain harvest)¹⁴³. These exports often lead to either a rapid decrease of available
626 nutrients and production in soils of developing countries, or the application of mineral fertilizer
627 to maintain a high level of production such as in intensive cropping systems. It has also been
628 reported that approximately 50% of the applied N fertilizer is lost in the environment^{20,144}.
629 Several regions of the world have adopted policies to reduce mineral fertilizer applications as
630 such applications seriously harm climate and ecosystem health, and rely on depleting mineral
631 deposits^{145,146}. Our review suggests that practices promoting synchrony can help to decrease
632 mineral fertilizer amounts while maintaining, or even increasing, production. This may result
633 from 1) a reduction of nutrient losses (70% for N) enhancing nutrient use efficiency¹³², 2) a
634 better use of water and light resources (+22%¹³⁷) by reducing the nutrient limitation of plant
635 growth and periods of bare soil, and 3) the mobilization of nutrients from natural reserves
636 (atmospheric N₂ and soil minerals), which can represent several hundred kilograms per hectare
637 and per year for N¹⁴⁷. Managing synchrony may therefore have important implications for the
638 economic and environmental outcomes of modern agriculture. Nevertheless, it is important to
639 keep in mind that the reservoir of rock-derived nutrients has limits, especially in old highly-

640 weathered soils, and the long-term sustainability (decades-centuries) of agrosystems relies on a
641 balance between nutrient inputs and outputs at field scale, in particular through practices
642 promoting organic nutrient recycling (Figure 6).

643 We have focused our discussion on plant functional diversity as the simplest, and most
644 informed (in terms of impacts), way to manage synchrony in agrosystems. However, our
645 framework points to other key components of synchrony such as soil diversity, plant/microbial
646 phenotypes and quantity/quality of organic matter inputs. Considering these components
647 suggests other synchrony-promoting practices that are ready-to-use such as field inoculation
648 with microbes^{148,149}, or deserve long-term research such as the breeding of new crop
649 varieties/species^{150,151} (Figure 6). Managing synchrony will systematically require a systemic
650 approach and a combination of practices.

651 In conclusion, some of the management practices identified as promoting synchrony
652 have already been tested and shown to be effective in reducing nutrient losses and fertilizer use
653 and/or improving biomass production and soil C storage under specific conditions. The recent
654 insights synthesized here draw out the conditions of success of these practices in terms of
655 pedoclimatic context and combination with other practices (Figure 6). This synthesis also
656 suggests new management options based on plant traits (e.g., amount and type of
657 rhizodeposition, content of condensed tannins in litter) that should help improve agrosystem
658 sustainability, including in the most difficult pedoclimatic conditions (e.g., sandy soils, long
659 season without plant activity). Future priorities are to (1) integrate this scientific knowledge
660 into tools used by practitioners for redesigning agrosystems, (2) develop methods/proxies to
661 quantify the level of synchrony and (3) continue efforts to fill knowledge gaps on the synchrony
662 in various natural ecosystems. In particular, additional research is needed to better understand
663 i) the mechanisms of FreeOM synchrony under conservative herbaceous plants, ii) quantities
664 of nutrients that can be released from rocks *via* the Sync-Inorganic each year to compensate
665 nutrient outputs, iii) the synergies and trade-offs between synchrony systems and iv) the
666 resistance and resilience of the different synchrony systems to disturbances (e.g., climate, plant
667 cutting and harvest). These advances will allow future cropping systems to better benefit from
668 nature-based solutions.

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Synchrony	Conditions of synchrony	Combination of practices to set up for promoting the targeted synchrony
Sync-MAOM	-Acquisitive plant species -Continuous activity of microbes M & I -Reserve of MAOM in soil	- Use/breeding of acquisitive species with strong capacity of stimulating nutrient mineralization/immobilization, e.g. high C rhizodeposition - The carbon:nutrient ratio of plant species or organic residues must be high enough to induce nutrient immobilization. Ideally, the different plant species have contrasting carbon:nutrient ratios (a, c, l, j, k) - Maintaining a continuous cover of active plants fueling microbes in energy-rich C (all pictures but e) - Recycling organic nutrients at local scale (farm-watershed) to preserve soil organic reserve on the long-term (d, e, f)
Sync-FreeOM	-Conservative plant species -Mycorrhizal fungi -Reserve of FreeOM in soil	- Use/breeding of conservative species producing recalcitrant litter with reactive compounds fixing organic nutrients (e, f)* - Or/and amendment of recalcitrant organic residues harboring reactive compounds more or less charged in organic nutrients (e) - Recycling organic nutrients at local scale (farm-watershed) to preserve soil organic reserve on the long-term (d, e, f)
Sync-Inorganic	-Plant symbiosis with mycorrhizal fungi & N ₂ fixing bacteria -Nutrients stored in bedrock, soil minerals and/or precipitates	- Use/breeding of species with strong capacity of mobilizing nutrients from rock and soil minerals, e.g. mycorrhized roots exerting strong mechanic pressure on minerals, secreting high amount of organic acids & ligands - Use of plant with deep roots colonizing bedrock (g, h, i) - Use of legumes (a, c, k) - Inoculation with mixed mycorrhizal fungi & N ₂ fixing bacteria in highly degraded soils
Sync-Market	-Plant species with complementary nutritional needs -Common mycorrhizal networks	- Mixing plant species with different nutrient acquisition strategies and carbon:nutrient ratios (a, c, l, j, k) - Promoting perennial plants (f, g, h, l, k) and/or permanent plant cover (all pictures but e) to fuel mycorrhizae in energy-rich carbon - No or limited use of soil tillage (b) and pesticides to preserve mycorrhizae networks - Inoculation with mixed mycorrhizal fungi in highly degraded soils
Increasing overall synchrony	-Synchrony systems adapted to pedoclimatic context -Complementary synchrony systems -Plant plasticity & reserve	- Analyzing the soil profile and climate, defining the most adapted synchrony systems - Mixing plant species with different nutrient acquisition strategies (a, c, l, j, k) - Breeding crops species for their suitability to association - Promoting perennial plants with high reserve and organ plasticity (f, g, h, l, j, k)

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674 **Figure 6.** Combinations of agricultural practices promoting synchrony between soil nutrient supply and plant nutrient demand through the four major systems of coordination
675 of plant-soil functions synthesized in this framework (Sync-MAOM, Sync-FreeOM, Sync-Inorganic, Sync-Market). Some practices can enhance the overall synchrony in
676 agrosystems by improving the efficiency of each system of coordination and by combining several systems of coordination. Photographs illustrate examples of practices
677 promoting synchrony. Some of them have ancestral origins (f, g, j), others have been developed and tested in the last decades (a, b) or are still under development in agricultural
678 research centres and/or farmers' networks. (c, d, h, k). (a) relay cropping with soybeans sown during barley growth (©ARVALIS/GENDRE Sophie); (b) direct drill on a rolled
679 barley cover (©ISARA/VINCENT-CABOUD Laura); (c) mixture of twelve species of annual crops that (d) was consumed as a standing crop by sheep (©A2C/THOMAS
680 Frédéric); (e) production of compost used as a substrate in market gardening or as an amendment in agriculture. Once stabilized, the compost is composed of recalcitrant plant
681 residues enriched with microbial compounds (©INRAE/MAITRE Christophe); (f) extensive grazing of heathlands (©SHUTTERSTOCK); (g) the “bread-tree” *Artocarpus altilis*
682 (©SHUTTERSTOCK) and (h) the cereal *Thinopyrum intermedium* (©ISARA/DUCHENE Olivier) are two examples of perennial plants that can be used as source of
683 carbohydrates and proteins; (i) agroforestry associating a barley crop with a walnut tree plantation (©INRAE/NICOLAS Bertrand); (j) association of banana, pineapple and
684 pepper plantations (©A2C/THOMAS Frédéric); (k) wheat cultivation on a living clover cover (©ISARA/DUCHENE Olivier); (l) cover cropping with mustard (©INRAE/WEBER
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686 Literature

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Supplementary 1. The dominant paradigm of nutrient (N taken as a model here) cycling, up to the end of the 2000's.

The mineralization of soil organic N has long been considered as the major bottleneck restricting supply of N to plants (blue arrows in the Figure below, depolymerization being considered the limiting step in the mineralization process). Indeed, a large part of N present within plant litter is not released as mineral N during decomposition but incorporated and maintained into soil organic N for several decades to centuries³⁰⁻³³. Moreover, microbial mineralization of soil organic N was conventionally viewed and modelled as a process whose velocity is controlled by soil N content and environmental factors ($d/dt N = -k.N$), and not by the plant^{34,35}. According to this paradigm, the soil supply of mineral N is decoupled from the plant demand and is the limiting process for plant growth in most ecosystems (soil supply \ll plant demand)³⁶. This view was so pervasive that it continues to shape current-day vocabulary, with the concept of soil fertility still used to explain differences in plant communities and primary production between environments (e.g. plants from nutrient-rich versus nutrient-poor soils)^{24,37,38}. This view largely influences the representation of the nutrient cycle in models in ecology and biogeochemistry^{35,39,40}.

Although some support for these ideas can be found in cultivated soils⁴¹, research over these last two decades has deeply modified our knowledge on nutrient cycling, especially in natural ecosystems. A first revision of the classical paradigm was made in 2000's to include the ability of some plants and their mycorrhizal associates to uptake dissolved organic N and to compete for mineral N with microbes^{41,42} – represented by orange arrows in the figure. There is now a growing body of studies demonstrating the ability of plants to control most soil N fluxes⁴³⁻⁴⁶ – represented by green dashed arrows in the figure. This calls for an overhaul of our vision of nutrient cycles^{47,48}.

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Supplementary 2. Expected contribution to ecosystem functioning of the synchrony system based on a common nutrient market (Sync-Market) in relation to pedoclimatic contexts and plant functional diversity.

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